

DESIGNING THE VR PROBE: AN INTRODUCTORY APPLICATION TO VIRTUAL REALITY FOR PEOPLE LIVING WITH DEMENTIA (PLWD)

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VIRTUAL REALITY (VR)

- VR uses a combination of visual, audio and sometimes haptic feedback to provide an immersive experience (Kim et al., 2017).
- VR technology has become more accessible with the release of devices like the HTC Vive (Robertson, 2015) and the Oculus Quest (Dingman, 2021).
- The use of VR in research has increased thanks to this.
- One such area includes the use of VR for people living with dementia (PLWD).

DEMENTIA

- Dementia is a neurodegenerative condition which causes a gradual decline in cognitive functionality over time (WHO, 2020).
- Over 55 million people have been diagnosed with dementia with 10 million new cases being found every year (WHO, 2020).
- There is currently no cure for dementia (WHO, 2020).
- Research has found that non-pharmacological activities can enrich the lives of PLWD (Shigihara et al., 2020).

DEMENTIA AND VR

- The use of technology like VR provides opportunities to support PLWD (e.g. assessment, monitoring, support for cognitive and physical functioning (Astell et al., 2019)).
- VR Interventions can provide various beneficial outcomes for PLWD (e.g. improving memory performance (Byrns et al., 2020) or recalling motor tasks (Fenney and Lee, 2010)).
- VR can provide old and new experiences for PLWD without the complications of travel (Möhler et al., 2020).
- The use of VR has become more important with the increased sense of isolation among PLWD as a result of Covid-19 restrictions (Curelaru et al., 2021).

INTRODUCING VR TO PLWD

91% of PLWD were diagnosed after the age of 65 (WHO, 2020).

PLWD involved in research likely have no prior experience using VR (Flynn et al., 2022a).

Commercially available introductions to VR exist, they lack effective design considerations for older adults (Abeelee et al., 2021).

The aim of this VR probe is to allow PLWD to experience VR and to inform design decisions for future VR applications (Hutchinson et al., 2003).

SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The VR Probe was created using Unity3D for its popularity in creating cross-platform 2D and 3D games (González et al., 2017).

The use of the XR Interaction Toolkit (Unity3D, 2023) allows for the creation of VR applications.

The interaction system manages interactions between the user and virtual objects in the environment.

The toolkit provides an easy to set up virtual representation.

Designed to work on the Oculus Quest 2 for ease of use anywhere (Saredakis et al., 2021).

TASK DESIGN

- Simple tasks to replicate common actions in VR were designed following the Responsive, Engaging, Augmenting, Failure-Free (REAFF) framework (Astell, 2009).

Selection

Object Placement

Gaze

Teleportation

TASK INSTRUCTIONS

- Each task has a UI panel displaying instructions to prompt the participants to perform the task.
- The use of prompts can improve the functional independence of PLWD (Braley et al., 2018).
- An encouraging message appears when the participant completes the task, PLWD respond faster to positive feedback (Maki et al., 2018).

MANAGING INTERACTION

High interaction fidelity leads to a greater sense of immersion (Rogers et al., 2019).

Interaction rays were added to the virtual hands to avoid physical strain and for its ease of use (Argelaguet and Andujar, 2013).

All hand interactions use the trigger button on the controller to reduce cognitive load.

An extra interaction ray is attached to the head to manage gaze interactions.

LOCOMOTION

- Locomotion allows participants to move the virtual representation in the VR space (Bozgeyikli et al., 2016).
- Various locomotion methods exist (e.g joystick movement, teleportation, arm-cycling (Coomer et al., 2018)).
- Teleportation was chosen for its ease of use compared to other locomotion systems.
- Teleportation anchors were placed beside each task where the participants can point the interaction rays at the task and press the trigger button to teleport to that location.

MULTISENSORY DESIGN

- Using a combination of visual, audio and haptic feedback can provide a greater sense of immersion (Muñoz et al., 2022), and can support participants with impaired senses (Hodge et al., 2018).
- The interaction rays change colour when they hover over interactable objects, the controllers will also vibrate.
- Interactable objects will gain an outline or change colour as the participant hovers over the object.
- Visual and haptic feedback will inform the user where they can teleport to.

VIRTUAL REPRESENTATION

- A virtual avatar is a visual representation of the user within the VR environment (Hodge et al., 2018).
- PLWD can accept the virtual hands as their own while using VR (Matsangidou et al., 2020), and can accept other virtual avatars in the same environment (Mendez et al., 2015).
- Full body avatars were initially considered but caused disembodiment due to inconsistent movement between the virtual and real forearms.
- Virtual hands were included as they move consistently with the controllers.

CONTRIBUTIONS & FUTURE WORK

This VR Probe has been used in a study to introduce older PLWD to VR (Flynn et al., 2022b).

Findings from this study were used to improve the VR Probe (e.g. inclusion of anti-aliasing and including background audio).

Future studies will gather gameplay and interview data to gain more insight to how PLWD navigate VR and engage with task-based activities.

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VR PROBE DEMO VIDEO

- Scan the QR Code for a showcase video of the VR Probe.

THANK YOU FOR LISTENING

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